

Project Deliverable

D5.3 Impact Factsheets

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Introduction – EU policy making

EU policy has been a persistent force for advancing towards a more gender equal academia. Various cycles of revised policy making have gone from “fixing” the women (e.g. skills training and mentoring), to “fixing” the institutions (implementation of gender equality plans) towards “fixing” the knowledge (integrating a gender dimension in research methods and content). The GEDII project contributes to the latter by examining how gender issues affect the collaborative production of knowledge by research teams.

Why is the EU level policy making important?

Gender equality is a cross-cutting issue at EU policy level including the EU Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality (2016-2019), a priority for the European Research Area (ERA) or dedicated funding regarding implementation of gender equality plans in the H2020. Whereas policy measures have targeted largely individuals or organizations, the team- or group level issues have received much less attention. Two EU policy areas where GEDII insights on the gender aspects of R&D teams are especially relevant can be identified. First, ERA priority 4 *Gender Equality and Gender Mainstreaming in Research* which focuses on 1) Scientific Careers, 2) Gender Balance in Decision Making, and 3) Integration of Gender Dimension in Research. Second, the gender aspects of team work have important consequences for assessing and monitoring the impact on research participation and quality of H2020 and European Research Council (ERC) funding. In addition, other important EU level policy schemes such as the Human Resource Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R implemented by Euraxess) are relevant from a gender perspective because of overlap with the criteria often included in GEPs, and hence should incorporate team level considerations, such as gender balance in who is invited to join the team and what role they are allocated.

Key points and recommendations

Currently there are no policy actions that would specifically target gender aspects at the team level within Europe. An important point of departure therefore consists of indicating how GEDII results interface or potentially impact existing policy initiatives, especially as the importance of team science is growing trend and membership of a team is an important aspect of PostDoc training.

- Although science has become a team effort, scientific careers are evaluated based on individual merits. The EU policy level should become an important driving force in establishing schemes to explicitly recognize team efforts and the distribution of credit for individual researchers. This is an unresolved issue that needs to be addressed across various initiatives such as Human Resource strategies (HRS4R) and gender equality initiatives (ERA priority) alike.
- More gender inclusive teams are a means to address the gender productivity gap between women and men in science. R&D teams are thus an all-important area of intervention for retaining women in science and advancing their careers, addressing thus ERA Priority objectives 1) + 2)

- GEDII has direct relevance for the ERA Priority objective 3) to integrate the gender dimension in research methods and content by emphasizing that gender aspects can bias the production of quality knowledge.
- R&D teams constitute an all-important organizational-, scientific- and often social context where individual researchers develop their work. As such, the team environment and team climate shape the experience of conducting research in important ways and play a key role regarding decisions to stay-on or to leave. Addressing the ERA Priority objective of women participation in science, GEDII underscores the importance of supportive team climate for both attracting and retaining women in science.

An important new instrument for monitoring gender aspects at the team level along these lines is the Gender Diversity Index developed by the GEDII project. It is a composite indicator to measure the participation of women and men in teams in a more elaborate way across seven pillars including age, education, care responsibilities, marital status, type of contract, seniority and team tenure.

- Integrated into H2020 proposal writing, the GDI can provide a more elaborate account on the gender inclusiveness of the applicant team beyond simply counting the “women on the team”, taking into account equal representation and attrition along 7 pillars.
- The GDI is a valuable new instrument for monitoring the potential impact of more gender inclusive teams on research performance. At the EU policy level this could be achieved through integrating GEDII tools into the next round of ERC or H2020 monitoring.
- The Gender Diversity Index should be incorporated into the design of Gender Equality Plans (GEP) via existing instruments such as the GEAR tool to raise awareness regarding the importance of gender aspects for teams and monitor the potential impact of GEP measures.

Five Must Reads

Sarsons, Heather. 2017. “Recognition for Group Work: Gender Differences in Academia.” *American Economic Review: Papers and Proceedings* 107 (5): 141–45. → *Pitfalls of gender blind credit allocation*

Slater, Amy. 2018. “Top Tips for Gaining Recognition on Team Science Projects | The Academy of Medical Sciences.” April 24, 2018. <https://bit.ly/2CGjzKx> → *Practical credit allocation tips for collaborative research*

European Commission. 2016. “Horizon 2020 Annual Monitoring Report 2015.” Commission Staff Working Document SWD(2016) 376 final. Brussels. <https://bit.ly/2D5B0Ej>

National Research Council (U.S.), Nancy J. Cooke, and Margaret L. Hilton, eds. 2015. *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*. Washington, D.C: The National Academies Press. → *Excellent state of the art regarding team science*

Bennett, Michelle L., Howard Gadlin, and Christophe Marchand. 2018. “Collaboration and Team Science: A Field Guide. 2nd Edition.” 18–7660. National Cancer Institute, U.S. Department of Health & Human Service. → *Excellent practitioners guide to building effective teams*

Introduction – Human Resource Management

There is ample evidence that all key aspects of an organization are hallmarked by an inequality regime, be it the organizational structure, job profiles or the organizing of work. So far, however, attention has yet to focus on the level below that of organizations, which for many institutions – particularly those that rely on high skills levels such as research performing organizations – is the level at which much of the interactions take place. HR policies and interventions to promote greater gender diversity in organizations have yet to be more fully deployed at the level of the team. Consequently, HR departments are well advised to consider team level dynamics when designing their interventions.

Why is it important to target teams with HR interventions?

The link between diversity and performance is complex and calls for more comprehensive approaches to HR that include every aspect of a researcher's employment. The GEDII project shows that there is no direct relationship between gender diversity and team performance. However, HR professionals can nevertheless affect the team context and create a healthy and engaging work environment. HR should ensure that recruitment to a team is fair and inclusive so that it leads to more congenial and inclusive environments for researchers, as well as prevent dominant societal stereotypes to create optimal conditions which foster overall organizational performance.

Key points and recommendations

The effectiveness of gender interventions in HR has been fiercely debated. So far, corporations have paid huge sums in diversity training programs, with only limited results. Evidence suggests that, at best, results last only in the short-term, and at worst, can create a backlash. Research also suggests that managers who believe they operate in a meritocratic environment might be more prone to make biased decision. So what would work instead?

- Train employees in engaging or managing team problem solving processes: Research shows that mandatory diversity trainings can activate biases. Moreover, managers can become resistant if they feel their autonomy is affected. Instead of promoting short trainings as remedies, employees should be invited to engage, for instance, in mentoring programs for women and minorities. If people work with colleagues from minority groups, they are more likely to become equality champions. This is further supported if there are mechanism that prepare and empower to implement meaningful changes within the organization.
- Employee training should target three distinct levels of team collaboration: the team knowledge (shared mental models, task understanding), the team skills (communication assertiveness), and team attitudes (trust, psychological safety, cohesion). Scientific leadership is one among several other ingredients of effective teams.
- Monitor teams against the Gender Diversity Index. Evidence shows that monitoring, reporting and

reflecting on gender diversity within teams supports efforts towards inclusion. One main benefit of the Gender Diversity Index is that it goes beyond 'counting heads' and captures the outcomes of gendered processes. The Gender Diversity Index calculates a team score that reflects how inclusive it is and thus emphasizes areas where practices might need to be examined. However, it should not be used as a tool to fix 'others', but instead should be considered as a tool to help address inequalities and biases more profoundly.

- Make the tools and initiatives for greater inclusion more easily accessible. Promote mutual learning by enabling employees to effectively interact with a wide range of people in the organization. This should allow everybody to formulate private opinions and concerns without before these are explored in a moderated discussion. This behavioral, cognitive and affective learning process should be extended beyond single interventions and be conducted within a safe environment.
- Become aware of micro practices: Formal policies are often in place, which reflect efforts to achieve greater gender equality. Standardized routines are devised in an attempt to remove biases, but in practice are ineffective if they are not followed or taken seriously. It is also important to check whether specific criteria are implicitly gendered, for example in recruitment or promotion processes. Are all specified requirements really necessary? For instance, do all people in leadership roles have to be present full time or work overtime? Moreover, micro practices often undermine objective criteria. For instance, the perception of performance might be altered by non-performance related factors, such as likeability. The potential effects of micro practices need to be analyzed to ensure the effectiveness of gender equality policies.

Five Must Reads

National Research Council (U.S.), Nancy J. Cooke, and Margaret L. Hilton, eds. 2015. *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*. Washington, D.C: The National Academies Press.

Acker, Joan (2006) 'Inequality Regimes: Gender, class, and race in organizations', *Gender & Society* 20(4), 441-464.

Dobbin, Frank and Kalev, Alexandra (2016) 'Why Diversity Programs Fail. And what works better.', *Harvard Business Review* (July-August), 1-10.

Fujimoto, Yuka and E.J. Härtel, Charmine (2017) 'Organizational diversity learning framework: going beyond diversity training programs', *Personnel Review* 46(6), 1120-1141.

Vinkenburg, Claartje J. (2017) 'Engaging Gatekeepers, Optimizing Decision Making, and Mitigating Bias: Design Specifications for Systemic Diversity Interventions', *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science* 53(2), 212-234.

Introduction – Team leadership

Research management is increasingly complex. Heterogeneous demands are placed on research group leaders through heightened accountability combined with tight competition for increasingly scarce funds. Disciplinary and strictly scientific exigencies run in parallel to more societal oriented agendas such as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) while research itself increasingly requires an entrepreneurial approach. The research group is the basic organizational unit under the direct management of the team leader where these demands are played out.

Why are team leaders important?

Research group leaders have a pivotal position in-between the wider research environment and the direct management of human resources and social relations “in the lab”. Leaders are responsible for developing a resource strategy, the management of the research process itself (staff hiring, team climate), motivating peers through their scientific leadership as well as securing the visibility and collaboration network of the group. Gender and wider diversity aspects are important across these team dimensions. Apart from the organizational context, team leaders are key for setting the overall attitude towards gender issues inside the team that range from monitoring equal participation of all team members to guaranteeing a safe, harassment free environment.

Key points and recommendations

Having a competitive but cohesive research team depends on many factors that can broadly be divided into two areas: first, access to a diverse set of resources (funds, ideas, knowledge, etc.) and second, the management of these (diverse) resources in order to achieve the team's (scientific) vision. The key process to highlight is “information integration” during which team members collaborate in order to convert distributed, personal information and experience into new knowledge. Gender bias can undermine this team effort – with team leaders holding a key position to mitigate its effects.

- Awareness raising concerning gender bias in science and teams is a crucial first step. However, lecture based anti-bias training without transfer to real work contexts is of limited value. Team leaders can actively challenge stereotypes by facilitating regular contact among all team members and alternating roles and responsibilities among staff such as inclusion of seniors and more juniors roles in decision-making. Leaders should challenge team members concerning their socio-cultural assumptions regarding their colleagues.
- Among the most important elements of a well-functioning team is mutual “trust” among its members. Researchers and other staff need to feel safe in order to voice potentially “risky” ideas or be critical with peers. Team leaders are vital for nurturing a healthy team climate for example through team building activities. In addition, leaders attitudes towards harassment and mistreatment set the overall tone of what is “tolerated”, enforcing organizational policies

and hence a safe work environment.

- The importance of effective communication can hardly be overstated for well-functioning teams. However, status and power hierarchies condition which information gets shared. Leaders need to assure equal participation of women and men across junior and seniority roles in meetings and make sure all voices are heard. Conflict can be a valuable resource to prevent premature conclusions – but needs to be monitored in order to not spiral out of control.
- Nonverbal communication (eye contact, turn-taking, body posture) is important for the reproduction of gendered interaction hierarchies. These semi-automatic gestures are hard to address and change. Newer research shows that simple tricks such as taking team members for a walk breaks up confrontational and exposed communication settings (meetings) in favor of less biased, safer interaction styles.
- Team leaders are also responsible for establishing mechanism within the team for distribution the credit of collective work. Given the positive role of teams for mitigating the productive gap between women and men, team leaders have to assure fair and transparent allocation rules that benefit all members equally.
- A variety of team training schemes do exist that assist team leaders to be attentive not just the scientific leadership but to foster and train team skills (e.g. communication) as well as team attitudes (trust, team orientation). “Cross-training” specifically can help teams to develop knowledge about roles and capabilities of diverse team members.

Five Must Reads

Bennett, Michelle L., Howard Gadlin, and Christophe Marchand. 2018. “Collaboration and Team Science: A Field Guide. 2nd Edition.” 18–7660. National Cancer Institute, U.S. Department of Health & Human Service. → *Excellent practitioners guide to building effective teams*

Vaan, Mathijs de, Balazs Vedres, and David Stark. 2015. “Game Changer: The Topology of Creativity.” *American Journal of Sociology* 120 (4): 1144–94. → *Thorough analysis of how to pitch for innovative teams*

Ridgeway, Cecilia L. 2008. “Framed Before We Know It: How Gender Shapes Social Relations.” *Gender & Society* 23 (2): 145–60. → *Clarifies how gender affects and potentially biases group interactions*

National Research Council (U.S.), Nancy J. Cooke, and Margaret L. Hilton, eds. 2015. *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*. Washington, D.C: The National Academies Press. → *Extensive section on team leadership across the seven dimensions of team science.*

Meyer, Bertolt, Michael J. Burtscher, Klaus Jonas, Sebastian Feese, Bert Arnrich, Gerhard Tröster, and Carsten C. Schermuly. 2016. “What Good Leaders Actually Do: Micro-Level Leadership Behaviour, Leader Evaluations, and Team Decision Quality.” *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology* 25 (6): 773–89. → *Nonverbal leadership behavior*

Introduction – Research Funding Organizations

Most research nowadays is carried out in teams, often across disciplinary, organizational and national boundaries. Instruments to monitor and assess the impact of team composition – specifically from a gender perspective – on research processes and outcomes are scarce. The GEDII project provides new tools and evidence to better understand how gender and diversity should be addressed on the team level in order to guarantee a more just science system and better quality research. Supporting equality concerns remains a pressing challenge in the face of an increasingly diverse and demanding R&D funding landscape.

Why are Funding Organizations important?

Success in competitive research funding is an important measure of scientific excellence. Several gender issues are well known to interfere in the just distribution of funding such as the under-representation of women in gatekeeper positions, the bias of review processes, gendered definitions of excellence or the penalty of carrying out interdisciplinary research. At the same time, the rise of team science poses new demands on funding organizations that have to consider the unique new challenges of funding teams instead of individuals such as group size, geographic distribution, or knowledge integration in interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary research. An innovative policy agenda for addressing the gender challenge in research funding needs to pay attention to team level which is key for the success of the overall research and gender equality issues such as career advancement.

Key points and recommendations

- Evaluating and funding collaborative projects requires to consider team size and team complexity as distinct success criteria of projects. Larger teams with higher levels of diversity face greater difficulties of knowledge integration. Coordination and integration costs should be considered and explicitly accounted for in research proposals, especially for interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary projects.
- Funding organizations can provide incentives for team science by facilitating team-based awards and develop new standards for distribution of collective credit and its recognition during proposal review processes.
- The GEDII project has developed the Gender Diversity Index, a monitoring and assessment tool targeting specifically the team level. It is a composite indicator to measures the participation of women and men in teams in a more elaborate way across 7 pillars including age, education, care responsibilities, marital status, type of contract, seniority and team tenure.
- Funding organizations can use the GDI as a more sophisticated instrument to assess the gender

inclusiveness of applicant teams beyond simply counting the “women on the team”. Assessing gender diversity across the 7 pillars will raise awareness among researchers beyond simply “ticking the gender box”.

- The Gender Diversity Index is a valuable new instrument for monitoring the potential impact of more gender inclusive teams on research performance by tracking the productivity (number of publications) as well as quality (citations) of their funded research.
- Funding organizations are in a privileged position to promote further research on the relationships between gender diversity in teams and research performance, beyond the GEDII project. In order to consolidate our findings, follow up studies across disciplines and S&T fields are warranted across Europe, supported by more targeted funding for team science initiatives.
- The results of the GEDII cross-country survey indicate no effect of the Gender Diversity Index score on research performance among 86 teams. However, future research has to address our findings with larger and different samples of research teams.

Five Must Reads

European Commission, ed. 2009. *The Gender Challenge in Research Funding: Assessing the European National Scenes*. EUR 23721. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities. → *Exposes the multifaceted nature of gender in research funding.*

National Research Council (U.S.), Nancy J. Cooke, and Margaret L. Hilton, eds. 2015. *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*. Washington, D.C: The National Academies Press. → *Excellent overview of team science dimensions in general and consequences for research funding in particular.*

Besselaar, Peter van den, and Ulf Sandström. 2017. “Vicious Circles of Gender Bias, Lower Positions, and Lower Performance: Gender Differences in Scholarly Productivity and Impact.” *PLOS ONE* 12 (8): e0183301. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0183301>. → *unequal performance opportunities for women and men create “vicious circles” re-enshrining women’s lower position and status in academia.*

Bol, Thijs, Mathijs de Vaan, and Arnout van de Rijt. 2018. “The Matthew Effect in Science Funding.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 115 (19): 4887–90.

Nielsen, Mathias Wullum. 2017. “Gender Consequences of a National Performance-Based Funding Model: New Pieces in an Old Puzzle.” *Studies in Higher Education* 42 (6): 1033–55.

Introduction – Gender and Science Policy

Gender and Science (G&S) policy making has focused predominantly on the individual level (e.g. mentoring schemes, skills training) and the organizational level (e.g. Gender Equality Plans for structural change). It thus fails to consider one of the most consistent trends in science, namely the fact that research is done in teams. This is problematic since many of the processes that cause and sustain existing gender inequalities within academia are linked to group processes and cannot as such be addressed on an individual or structural level. Teams in academia are a neglected but all important level for G&S policy making.

Why are teams important for Gender & Science policy making?

Gender equal- and well-functioning teams are not determined by a specific proportion of women and men team members. Inequalities are the sum of many small events played out on a daily basis rather than being the cause of static predispositions. Examining collaboration in teams puts the spotlight on the conscious and unconscious reproduction of gender hierarchies and stereotypes in academia. The team is the arena where individual researchers may – or may not – be able to fulfill their aspirations and potentials and hence stay in science or leave. G&S policy for teams is challenging because team (boundaries) can be fuzzy and range from informal exchanges across institutions to more formal arrangements of organizational work groups.

Key points and recommendations

The results from the GEDII project indicate dual gains to be obtained from addressing gender diversity on a team level both in terms of ensuring quality and effectiveness in the research process itself and in terms of addressing and advancing gender equality within academia.

- Making teams more inclusive promotes gender equality in academia at large. Both the GEDII project and earlier studies have demonstrated how content wise factors related to caring responsibilities, access to resources and decision making as well as the intricate web of daily personal contacts and communication patterns affect the outcome of team work both on an overarching and a more individual level.
- For gender diversity to have a positive impact on research performance it needs to be embedded in inclusive teams. Inclusiveness creates the foundation for individuals to take part in and contribute to research on equal terms; it is the catalyst that makes gender diversity function as a tool for better research processes.

Organizational policies and individual support measures establish the overall gender equality and diversity context for research teams. Team leaders, human resource management are key for the promotion of gender equality. More specific measures targeting the team level directly are needed.

- First, there is a need to analyze how existing G&S policy are adopted and operationalised on the team level. Institutional Gender Equality Plans should spell out how certain measures such as anti-bias training can become more effective when targeting the working environment of teams rather than isolated individuals. The transfer to real working context is key for effective diversity training.
- More explicit and transparent mechanisms that regulate the allocation of credit for collective work are needed. The [CRediT taxonomy](#) for example lists 14 categories to attribute contributing roles to authors on publications.
- A “code of conduct” including a policy on harassment can be part of the joint agreements made within the team. On a more general level team policies can include objectives and strategies regarding the distribution of work-tasks and resources (including mobility) or how care responsibilities should be handled.
- The GEDII project has developed the Gender Diversity Index, a monitoring and assessment tool targeting specifically the team level. It is a composite indicator to measures the participation of women and men in teams in a more elaborate way across 7 pillars including age, education, care responsibilities, marital status, type of contract, seniority and team tenure.

Five Must Reads

Garforth, Lisa, and Anne Kerr. 2009. “Women and Science. What’s the Problem?” *Social Politics*, 379–403. → How policy reinscribes & frames the “women in science” problem.

Sexual Harassment of Women: Climate, Culture, and Consequences in Academic Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2018. Edited by Paula A. Johnson, Sheila E. Widnall, and Frazier F. Benya. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24994>. → Documents systematic and widespread occurrence of sexual harassment in academia, detrimental to individuals and team efforts.

Brink, Marieke van den, and Yvonne Benschop. 2012. “Slaying the Seven-Headed Dragon: The Quest for Gender Change in Academia.” *Gender, Work and Organization* 19 (1): 71–92.

Ahmed, Sara. 2007. “‘You End up Doing the Document Rather than Doing the Doing’: Diversity, Race Equality and the Politics of Documentation.” *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 30 (4): 590–609. → Don't reduce equality work to paper-work

Haas, Hartmut. 2010. “How Can We Explain Mixed Effects of Diversity on Team Performance? A Review with Emphasis on Context.” *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal* 29 (5): 458–90. → Critical examination of diversity effects

The Gender Diversity Index

Teamwork is the number one global workforce trend according to the Deloitte “Global Human Capital Trends 2016”. So far, research on the link between gender diversity and effective teamwork is inconclusive, because gender diversity is limited to ‘counting heads’, that is the proportion of women and men. The Gender Diversity Index is a newly developed tool for monitoring the outcomes of gendered team processes in a more elaborated way. Seven grounds of diversity are included: age, educational level, care responsibilities, marital status, type of contract, seniority and team tenure (years of experience in the team).

The Gender Diversity Index is a composite indicator which combines data on those seven grounds into one figure. It is bound between 0 and 1, and measures both parity in representation in the most desirable categories (e.g. senior roles) or more inclusive categories (e.g. care responsibilities), as well as equal chances for women and men to access these categories (attrition) for each of the seven grounds. In other words, women and men should be equally represented in the more desirable or inclusive categories, and the 'pipeline' there should not be leaking.

The seven pillars of the Gender Diversity Index

Pillar	Representation (α)	Attrition (δ)
Age	Are women and men equally represented in the group above team average age?	Is representation at least as equal in the group above team average age compared to the group below team average age?
Education	Are women and men equally represented in the group who hold a doctorate?	Is representation at least as equal in the group with a doctorate compared to the group without?
Care responsibilities	Are women and men equally represented in the group who have current care responsibilities?	Is representation at least as equal in the group with current care responsibilities compared to the group without?
Marital Status	Are women and men equally represented in the group who are either married or cohabitating with their significant other?	Is representation at least as equal in the group that are married/cohabitating compared to the group that are not?
Type of contract	Are women and men equally represented in the group who have a permanent or tenured contract?	Is representation at least as equal in the group that holds permanent/tenured contracts compared to the group that do not?
Seniority	Are women and men equally represented in the group who hold a senior position?	Is representation at least as equal in the group that are in senior positions compared to the group that are not?
Team tenure	Are women and men equally represented in the group above the average team tenure (years of experience in the team)?	Is representation at least as equal in the group that have experience above average team tenure compared to the group that do not?

How to work with the Gender Diversity Index

These indicators are combined to calculate the Gender Diversity Index (online calculation tool is available at <https://www.gedii.eu/self-assessment-tool/>). The scores of the Gender Diversity Index capture how inclusive the team is. A score close to 1 reflects an inclusive team, but lower scores reflect issues that need further attention in one or more of the pillars. Both the overall score of the Gender Diversity Index and the different pillar should be examined separately to detect areas where improvements could be made. The following questions can be useful when it comes to developing actions based on the Gender Diversity Index: (1) in which areas is it necessary to improve representation and/or retention of team members; and (2) what would happen if another member joined or if a specific team member left the team?

The following table illustrates how the results of the Gender Diversity Index can be interpreted. The team consists of seven individuals and with four men and three women is near parity. However, it achieves a score on the Gender Diversity Index of just 0.36, illustrating the need for a more sophisticated measure than simply the proportion of women or men. Looking at the indicators, it is clear that this is because women and men do not have equal outcomes when it comes to education, team tenure, contractual terms or level of seniority.

Metrics	Gender Diversity Index		Variables	Women	Men
Age δ	0.67	0.77	Below team average age	2	2
Age α	0.89		Above team average age	1	2
Education δ	0	0	No doctorate	2	4
Education α	0		Doctorate	1	0
Care δ	1	1	No current care responsibilities	2	3
Care α	1		Current care responsibilities	1	1
Marital status δ	0.80	0.86	Not married or cohabiting	1	1
Marital status α	0.96		Married or cohabiting	2	3
Contract δ	0	0	Temporary / casual	2	4
Contract α	0		Permanent / tenured	1	0
Seniority δ	0	0	Junior researcher/Other	1	2
Seniority α	0		Senior researcher/Team leader	1	0
Tenure δ	0	0	Below average team tenure	2	4
Tenure α	0		Above average team tenure	1	0

Table 1: α : representation; δ : attrition. $n = 7$ for all indicators, with the exception of 'seniority' where $n = 5$ due to missing data.

To know more

The full reports are found at <https://www.gedii.eu/about/publications/>. To learn more about the Gender Diversity Index or how to apply it to your own field, please contact Dr. Anne Laure Humbert (a.humbert@brookes.ac.uk) and Dr. Elisabeth Anna Guenther (contact@elisabeth-anna-guenther.eu)